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DISCUSSION VISUALIZATION AND REFLECTION SYSTEM TO FACILITATE TEAM-BASED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Many universities have adopted collaborative learning approaches such as Project-Based Learning (PBL), where students work in teams. However, in collaborative learning, problems such as not developing appropriate conclusions within the time constraint or the conclusions deviating from the central theme occur. Based on recognizing these issues, we have developed a system that visualizes and analyses learners' discussions in collaborative learning in real-time and feeds back the results to the learners to encourage them to reflect on the results, leading to active and appropriate discussions. The system analyzes the number of words said by each learner per unit of time and the rate of frequent words in collaborative learning and displays this information on the learner's browser in real-time. We can use the system for ideas and meeting management by displaying the co-occurrence network diagram of frequent words and trends of words in a meeting. We have applied this system to collaborative learning in teams and evaluated its effectiveness and impact on team discussions. In the experiment for PBL II course students, the results showed that the scores of the four data representations were more than three, and 73.7% of students evaluate the system as helpful to the discussion.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Many universities have adopted collaborative learning approaches such as Project-Based Learning (PBL), where students work in teams. However, in collaborative learning, there are problems such as not developing appropriate conclusions within the time constraint[1]. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, online learning support should support active collaboration in such an environment. We also expect to improve the learning outcomes and learning environment by utilizing the digitization of education style. Initials Lastname2 et al. [2] developed a system to analyze and coordinate the discussion situation from nonverbal information. The system helps the team members estimate their roles and other learners' intentions objectively. Based on the research, our research questions focus on the following.

- (1) How to analyze discussion contents in real-time.
- (2) How to directly feedback the analysis results to the members.

1.2 Objectives

In order to further promote PBL activities, the objectives in this research are as follows.

- (1) To build a real-time speech analysis system in which students can review and understand their remarks in the language information.
- (2) To verify whether collaborative learning can be activated and improve the quality of discussion by visualizing and reviewing the speech and language information.
- (3) To propose a system that can guide project teams to achieve satisfactory results quickly.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Outline of the proposed system

We propose a prototype system that allows students to review team activities in real-time and transform them into better activities by visualizing their activities in real-time. Figure 1 shows the proposed system configuration diagram. Speech is visualized by texting the speech data and mining the text every short time unit. In addition, analysis results such as the number of words and the passage of frequent words are displayed on the browser immediately. We can use the system in two situations: to promote discussion activities, and the other is to improve the quality of discussion. The former can promote the increase of speech by visualizing PBL work progress and setting the target value. In the case of exceeding the target value, the second way can visualize the divergence/convergence tendency and frequent words. It can also promote the review according to the needs of learners.

2.2 Real-time performance of the system

Firstly, the transmitted voice data is textualized in real-time using the Google cloud platform(speech API). Secondly, we analyze the text-file output by Google Apps script through the automatic execution of the text-mining tool called KH coder[3]. Lastly, we show the latest analysis result on the browser. In the prototype system, errors and processing delay did not occur except in minimal utterances.

2.3 Representation of analysis results

Figure 2 shows four visual representations of the analysis results from the KH coder. In order to support facilitation, it shows the quantity of speech defined by the number of utterances per minute in Fig.2(a). We set a target value in advance if the utterances exceed the target, reminding students to improve discussion quality. Fig.2(b) shows the trend of divergence and convergence of dialogues. We set a reference value of divergence and convergence boundary. If the number of words exceeds this number, there is a convergence tendency; on the contrary, there is a divergence tendency. Fig.2(c) shows the time changes of the frequent

appearance words. It helps students create valuable ideas and opinions. The diagram networks of the co-occurrence words in Fig.2(d) show the current discussion topics.

Fig. 1. System configuration diagram

Fig. 2. Representation of analysis results

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Experimental conditions

We carried out to apply the proposed system to two PBL courses and evaluate the system's effectiveness. One PBL course called "PBL I" was conducted with the theme of "creating social-friendly applications." Seven third-grade students (two groups in total) were the subjects. We obtained the data of the first two days in the process of these decisions. After the PBL I, we slightly modified the system to reduce the processing time and represent more precise graphs. Another PBL course called "PBL II" was the international PBL which tries to propose solutions and prototypes given by enterprises and governmental offices. Sixty-seven students

consisting of 40 overseas students and 27 Japanese students organized nine groups in total, and we obtained the data for the first three days. After the experiments, we conducted questionnaires surveys to evaluate the usefulness of the system and its impact on the team discussion promotion.

3.2 Experimental results

Figure 3 shows the details of the four data representations. As a result, for PBL I, (a),(b),(c) representation obtained scores between two to three, but that of (d) is a little bit lower than others. After slight modifications of the system, the results for PBL II were improved in all the representation data, and their scores were more than three. It suggested that real-time processing and effective representation improves the performance of the system.

Fig. 3 Questionnaire results of the effectiveness of the four data representations.

In the questionnaire about the system's usefulness, 50% of the respondents in PBL I said that the proposed system was helpful to the discussion, and 50% of them said that they would like to use it in the future. Moreover, for the PBL II students, the questionnaire results showed that 73.7% of the respondents said that the proposed system was helpful to the discussion, and 68.4% of them said that they would like to use it in the future.

4 CONCLUSION

We proposed a system that visualizes and analyses PBL discussions in real-time and feeds back the results to the students to encourage them to reflect on their activities. For PBL II students, the results showed that the scores of the four data representations were more than three, and 73.7% of students evaluate the system as helpful to the discussion. In the future, we will consider the new application method to decide more flexible and specific evaluation criteria and add a new function to improve the reliability and practicability of the system.

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